

THE BIGGEST MISTAKES MADE BY PARENTS IN THE EDUCATION OF CHILDREN

Avezov Olmos Ravshanovich¹

Associate Professor of
olmosavezov85@gmail.com

Shavkatova Shakhnoza Pulot qizi²

Student of the Faculty of Pedagogy
shahnozashavkatova20@gmail.com

¹Bukhara State Pedagogical Institute

²Bukhara State University

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7030501>

ABSTRACT:

This article presents information based on the experiences of parents about the mistakes made by parents in the education of their children, and the use of incorrect methods in raising a child. And as a result of these mistakes, a number of cases, such as negative emotions and susceptibility to vices, are highlighted in the child's behavior.

Key words: psychophysiological, protection, hyperprotection, need, leadership, emotional rejection, hardness

Introduction: From the researches and observations conducted in our country, it became clear that due to the inexperience and wrong upbringing of some parents, serious changes are taking place in the child's psycho-physiological and social-psychological conditions. For example, especially in teenage children, very severe manifestations of this have been observed. The social status of a child whose parents are divorced also changes, his sociometric status in the classroom suddenly drops, his self-esteem deteriorates, he imagines that people around him have a negative attitude towards him, withdraws from the circle of friends, performs tasks with frustration, becomes involuntary.

Main part:

Protection is generally actions by one person aimed at supporting another person.

Hyperprotection is an excessive attention of parents to their children, which is manifested in the fact that they do not spare time, effort and attention for child education. That is, care is turned into a way of life by the father and mother, that is, for both the mother and the father, child education becomes the content of life.

Hyperprotection based on pampering care is the desire of parents to satisfy all the desires, wishes and needs of the child blindly, without criticism and

judgment, they protect the child from any difficulties and obstacles. he will be ready to protect, to fulfill all his wishes on the spot, to caress, to rejoice at his simple achievements, to not notice his mistakes, and caressing and caressing in mutual relations will become a habit. Especially when a boy reaches the age of adolescence, he wants to show his aspiration for leadership, because he is manly, critical, wants to be what everyone says in the circle of friends and peers, but on the other hand, in reality, he does not have such qualities.

Rather than coddling, hyper-protection based on excessive care implies that the parent pays attention to the child by controlling his every step and behavior. Therefore, this method of education is full of various prohibitions and restrictions ("it is not possible", "this is not possible"). A child who grows up in such conditions is usually unable to think independently and make independent decisions, but grows up angry and dissatisfied with many things, because he needs constant control, seeing all the directions of others. He gets used to being told and shown: he cannot prepare lessons without his mother, he cannot go out without his father.

Very strong immoral responsibility - in this case, the level of demands on the child from parents is high, but his original wishes, desires and needs are not taken into account. Thinking about the future of their child, parents feel responsible for their behavior and try to create a person in their personal imagination, to form a personality. For example, "you are our first-born, you have to take care of your siblings", meaning that he is deprived of responsible and difficult work, such as taking care of the younger members of the family or a sick family member.

Emotional rejection - in which the parents raise their child in such a way that he is regularly reminded that he is a worry, an excess burden in the life of the parents, and that without him, the life of the parents would be different. If this child is not the only one in the family, but there is another, cheaper, more beloved person, the situation is even worse, "if you weren't..." or the girl is told "if only there was a boy instead of you "... are often mentioned.

Obstinacy is similar to emotional rejection at first glance, but it is more open and severe. Strictness can take the form of beating a child directly from an early age, insulting, humiliating, or showing extreme indifference to the child's needs, as if not noticing his or her presence.

Results and discussion: In the case of emotional rejection and harshness, the child tries to grow up faster, make a living by himself, and get rid of parental pressure. In such a family, it becomes a habit to punish the child for one or

another behavior. Adults do not know that the child obeys the parents' judgment because of fear, and that this has bad consequences in the future, even if they know, this method seems effective for them. Methods such as guilt, punishment commensurate with guilt become a psychological factor that controls the child's behavior, and he learns to always look for the guilty in the future. According to Freud's theory, a child sentenced to such a punishment becomes more and more aggressive, grows up to be a vindictive person who intends to take pain from some object (smaller than himself, strangers, animals). According to data, at least 1% of children in America are victims of such upbringing in the family. American scientist S. D. Sherrits studied the negative impact of such strictness in the family on the behavior of children and parents, and focused on the changes that occur in their character. Cases of physically oppressing a child and beating him are characteristic of almost all social strata. Most of the women who were unlucky in life, work, or were victims of unhappy love, but gave birth to a child, have a tendency to take their pain from their child, which is becoming a life skill more and more. Especially under the influence of stress factors, parents (for example, the unemployed, the homeless, migrants who went to other places in search of work, victims of ethnic or financial conflicts, the poor) were born unable to solve their social problems. begins to take revenge on his child. Scientists have learned that the more difficult the problems in the marriage seem to the father or mother, the more likely they are to beat their child and take revenge on him.

Conclusion: Everyone should be able to control their emotions. Especially parents and educators. Regardless of whether this feeling is positive or negative. The children of people who could not control their emotions also became emotional and could not act and make decisions based on their mental potential. Whoever sees a negative trait in a child, the real cause of it is the parents themselves or their educators.

References:

- 1.G. Corey. Theory and Practice of Group Counseling. Brooks/Cole Publishing Company 2005
- 2.K. Nelson-Jones. The theory and practice of counseling. Cassell, 1995
- 3.U.M. Roziyev "Psychological consultation and psychocorrection"
- 4.G'. Shoumarov "Family Psychology"
- 5.Z. Ibodullayev "Medical psychology"
- 6.Vasila Karimova "Family Psychology"
- 7.<http://www.ziyo.net>
- 8.<http://www.koob.ru/news>

SCIENCE AND INNOVATION IN THE EDUCATION SYSTEM

International scientific-online conference

9.www.academic.ru

10.<http://www.bookap.by.ru>

11.<http://psylib.org.ua/index.html>

